

**HYBRID WORK SYSTEMS AND EMPLOYEE
PERFORMANCE OF SELECTED FAST MOVING
CONSUMER GOODS COMPANIES IN LAGOS
STATE, NIGERIA**

ISSN: 1533 - 9211

Magaji, N., Oloidi, S. O., Soetan, A. T.

Department of Business Administration and Marketing, School Management Sciences, Babcock University, Ilishan-Remo, Ogun State, Nigeria.

Abstract

Employee performance is a critical factor in organisational success and as organisations grapple with increasing competition and changing consumer demands, they are looking to hybrid work to help mitigate the effects of declining task performance, reducing contextual performance, poor adaptive performance and low employee engagement. This study aimed to determine the effect of hybrid work systems on employee performance of selected fast moving consumer goods (FMCG) companies in Lagos State, Nigeria. The study adopted survey research design using a well-structured survey questionnaire with modified six-point Likert type scale. The sample size of 375 managers was determined using Raosoft sample size calculator while simple random and proportionate sampling techniques were utilized to identify eligible managers and was taken through pre-diagnostic tests for normality (skewness and kurtosis), linearity (Pearson correlation coefficient), homoscedasticity (Bartlett's test) and multicollinearity (VIF). Data collected were analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics and multiple and hierarchical regression analysis were conducted to test the seven hypotheses. The results showed that hybrid work systems had positive significant effect on employee performance. On the moderation effect of work environment and organisation support on the relationship between hybrid work systems and employee performance, the results showed negative but statistically significant effect. However, when the two moderating variables were combined, the beta coefficient of work environment and organisation support were positive and statistically significant meaning that work environment and organisation support both moderate the relationship between hybrid work systems and employee performance. The study outcomes reinforced the need for organisations to embrace hybrid work dimensions of flexibility, employee experience and work enablers to boost the performance of their employees. The study recommended that FMCG organisations should prioritize true flexibility, ensure positive remote experiences for their employees and invest in remote work enablers to boost employee performance.

**CORRESPONDING
AUTHOR:**

Magaji, N
magajin@babcock.edu.ng

KEYWORDS:

Hybrid work, Employee performance, Task performance, Contextual performance, Adaptive performance, Employee engagement, Work environment, Organisation support

Received: 22 March 2025
Accepted: 10 April 2025
Published: 18 April 2025

TO CITE THIS ARTICLE:

Magaji, N., Oloidi, S. O., & Soetan, A. T. (2025). Hybrid work systems and employee performance of selected fast moving consumer goods companies in Lagos State, Nigeria. *Seybold Report Journal*, 20(4), 127–146. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.15236559](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15236559)

Introduction

As organisations confront increased competition caused by globalisation, technical breakthroughs, economic uncertainty, and changing consumer expectations, the importance of employee performance in maintaining organisational success cannot be emphasised. Employee performance has a direct impact on a company's capacity to fulfil its objectives since workers who meet or exceed expectations help to build a durable competitive advantage (Sugiarti et al., 2021). However, just having a workforce does not ensure success; instead, organisations want people with the necessary skills, knowledge, and attitude to drive performance across several dimensions, such as job execution, contextual contributions, adaptable capacities, and engagement levels. When these performance factors are compromised, organisations may experience reduced productivity and overall effectiveness (Agubosim et al., 2023). Organisations are using remote and hybrid work methods to overcome performance challenges. These provide workers with more flexibility, improve work-life balance, and boost morale, resulting in increased attention and productivity (Elomien et al., 2021). Inclusivity, employee experience, and access to work enablers are critical elements in determining employee performance results (Agboola et al., 2020).

The Fast-Moving Consumer Goods (FMCG) business poses distinct obstacles to employee performance in many regions. Due to increased work expectations, frequent product releases, and fierce rivalry, FMCG enterprises worldwide have challenges in task performance, contextual performance, adaptive performance, and employee engagement (Ridwan et al., 2020). In the United States, the industry's quick speed causes job overload, stress, and frequent mistakes, while high turnover rates undermine collaboration and contextual performance (Andreas, 2022; Iskanto, 2021). Similarly, in China, the demanding "996" work culture causes weariness, decreased teamwork, and difficulties adjusting to quick market changes (Dong & Loang, 2023). Employee engagement in Chinese FMCG enterprises is further hampered by a lack of autonomy and an overemphasis on fulfilling performance targets (Yan et al., 2020). Despite its fast expansion, Kenya's FMCG industry is confronted with issues such as economic insecurity, increased workloads, and low engagement levels owing to restricted professional progression prospects (Govender & Bussin, 2020). In Nigeria, infrastructural shortcomings, insufficient training, high turnover, and economic instability impede employee effectiveness, while low pay and long working hours lead to burnout and disengagement (Okoli et al., 2020; Omale et al., 2023). Hybrid work models can address these difficulties by increasing employee flexibility, lowering job-related

stress, and facilitating continuous learning via digital platforms (Ikyanyon & Agber, 2020; Okolocha, 2021). Organisations may increase productivity and flexibility and develop a more engaged workforce by enabling workers to mix remote and in-office work (Vincent, 2020). Hybrid work addresses not just current performance issues but also long-term innovation, resilience, and organisational success in a changing business environment (Orji & Yakubu, 2020).

Literature Review

2.1.1 Employee Performance

Employee performance refers to the efficiency and effectiveness with which employees complete their assigned tasks and contribute to achieving organisational goals (Obasi et al., 2024). It encompasses various aspects of an individual's work, including the quality, speed, and accuracy of their outputs, as well as their ability to meet deadlines and maintain consistent productivity levels (Adedokun et al., 2023). Employee performance is a critical determinant of an organisation's success, as it directly influences operational efficiency, customer satisfaction, and overall business outcomes (Uwazurike & Ezenwa-Adiuku, 2021). In the context of Fast-Moving Consumer Goods (FMCG) companies, where market competitiveness and quick product turnover are essential, high employee performance ensures that businesses remain agile and responsive to market demands (Ajayi et al., 2024). Employee performance can be evaluated through different metrics, including task performance, contextual performance, adaptive performance, and employee engagement, each of which contributes to an organisation's overall productivity and success (Sopiah et al., 2019).

Employee performance is characterized by several key factors. It involves the ability to effectively complete core tasks and responsibilities, ensuring that employees meet deadlines, maintain accuracy, and deliver high-quality outputs (Greco et al., 2021). Performance also encompasses activities that contribute to the overall organisational environment, such as collaboration, initiative, and support for colleagues, all of which help create a productive and positive work culture (Khaksar et al., 2023). Another important characteristic is adaptability, where employees can adjust and thrive in changing work conditions, learning new skills and handling unexpected challenges without compromising their job quality or output (AlDhaheri et al., 2023). High levels of employee performance offer several advantages. Strong performance leads to increased

efficiency in achieving job expectations, directly contributing to organisational success (Yangailo, 2023).

Employees who demonstrate a commitment to organisational values and goals help foster teamwork and collaboration, creating a supportive work environment that boosts overall productivity. High-performance expectations can create unhealthy competition among employees, leading to workplace conflict or a reduction in teamwork and collaboration. This can damage the overall organisational culture and erode trust between employees and management (Omran et al., 2021). Moreover, employees who constantly feel the pressure to perform at peak levels may struggle to adapt to changes or new challenges, as the emphasis on maintaining current performance standards can hinder their ability to learn new skills or embrace new responsibilities.

2.1.2 Hybrid Work Systems

Hybrid work systems are flexible arrangements that integrate in-office and remote work, allowing employees to choose their work location and methods for fulfilling their duties (Yating et al., 2024). This model integrates the advantages of traditional office environments with remote work to enhance employee satisfaction, productivity, and work-life equilibrium (Choudhury et al., 2020). Employees often divide their time between corporate locations and remote environments, facilitated by technology that enables communication and collaboration (Bastanchury-López & De-Pablos-Heredero, 2022). Hybrid work systems enhance operational efficiency by offering flexibility that accommodates employee expectations. Hybrid work systems are characterised by essential traits that improve employee experience and organisational effectiveness. They provide flexibility by allowing employees to choose their work schedule and location, leading to enhanced job satisfaction and work-life balance (Yating et al., 2024). They promote inclusivity by accommodating diverse employee needs, including family obligations and personal productivity preferences (Choudhury et al., 2020).

These technologies provide several advantages to individuals and enterprises. Enhanced flexibility enables employees to customise their work schedules and environments, hence improving job satisfaction, morale, and retention rates. They enhance organisational productivity by optimising both remote and in-office work dynamics, fostering collaboration and minimising disruptions (Yating et al., 2024). Notwithstanding these benefits, hybrid work settings present several

challenges. Remote workers may have communication and collaboration challenges due to feelings of isolation or alienation from their in-office counterparts, leading to misunderstandings and ineffective teamwork (Ucho et al., 2022). Moreover, disparities between remote and in-office employees may lead to prejudice in promotions and project allocations, causing remote workers to feel undervalued and demotivated (Williams et al., 2021). Certain occupations may be incompatible with remote work, and employees in these roles may have difficulties in the absence of direct oversight and practical support (Olson et al., 2023). Furthermore, the blurring of personal and professional boundaries in remote situations may lead to burnout because of the expectation of ongoing availability. These problems underscore the need for careful management to guarantee the success of hybrid work systems.

Empirical Review

Effect of Hybrid Work Systems on Employee Performance.

Several scholars (Aladejebi, 2021; Baakeel, 2021; Ekasari et al., 2022; Hackney et al., 2022; Kore et al., 2022; Moens et al., 2021; Qu & Yan, 2022; Tunk & Kumar, 2021) have investigated the effect of hybrid work systems on employee performance, with the majority of results indicating a significant positive impact. Susilo (2020) discovered that remote workers had more fun, happiness, and motivation, which led to better job performance. Similarly, Tunk and Kumar (2021) and Baakeel (2021) found that remote work improves productivity, communication, and job effectiveness. According to Moens et al. (2021), telework's efficiency leads to greater job satisfaction, work-life balance, and lower role stress. Ekasari et al. (2022) discovered that remote work improves both employee performance and work-life balance, while Hackney et al. (2022) discovered that non-mandatory remote work arrangements increase productivity and performance. Kore et al. (2022) highlighted organisational commitment and culture as critical elements in reinforcing the advantages of remote work for employee performance. However, Aladejebi (2021) contends that the influence of remote work on job performance is minimal.

Several research looked at the function of mediating variables in the link between hybrid work and employee performance. Wolor et al. (2021) discovered that remote work has a considerable impact on work discipline, which leads to improved performance. Liu et al. (2021) recognised job crafting as a method via which telework increases performance, while Ishak et al. (2022) identified

job motivation as a complete mediator of the influence of distant work on job performance. Choukir et al. (2022) identified employee attitudes and beliefs as crucial mediators, while Ekasari et al. (2022) found that work-life balance plays an important role in connecting distant work and employee performance. Despite the good results, a few research revealed opposing viewpoints. Wolor et al. (2021) determined that remote work had no substantial effect on employee performance. Kitagawa et al. (2021) discovered that remote workers often face productivity decreases as a result of bad home office setups and communication issues. Morikawa (2022) discovered that for many people and organisations in Japan, remote work productivity was only 60-70% of in-office productivity, citing diminished face-to-face contacts, poor communications infrastructure, and activities needing physical presence in the office.

Theoretical underpinnings

Technology Acceptance Theory

The Technology Acceptance Theory (TAT), introduced by Fred Davis in 1989, provides a foundational paradigm for understanding the adoption and use of personal technology. The theory posits two primary concepts: Perceived Usefulness (PU), denoting an individual's belief that a technology enhances performance, and Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU), indicating the notion that using the technology requires little effort (Davis, 1989). These factors influence perceptions of technology, affect behavioural intentions, and dictate actual adoption rates. The hypothesis is based on Fishbein and Ajzen's (1975) hypothesis of Reasoned Action (TRA) and is rooted in behavioural psychology.

TAT is particularly significant when examining employee acceptance of hybrid work arrangements that prioritise technology. The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), developed from the TAT, assesses employees' perceptions of digital technology regarding its utility and ease of use, influencing their likelihood to embrace hybrid work arrangements (Khatatbeh et al., 2023). Employees who see these systems as intuitive (high perceived ease of use) and beneficial for work-life balance, productivity, and flexibility (high perceived usefulness) are more inclined to adopt and implement them (Nguyen et al., 2020; Sjarifudin et al., 2023). The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) examines the impact of sustained technology utilisation and experience on employee performance and long-term adoption (Worthington et al., 2020).

Critics assert that the theory is constrained, but the consensus among several scholars about TAT's proposition that perceptions of utility and simplicity of use influence technology adoption (Bhattacharyya et al., 2020; Kim & Chang, 2022; Oamen, 2023). Critics contend that the Technology Acceptance Theory (TAT) inadequately considers the cultural, organisational, and environmental factors influencing technology acceptance (Gefen & Straub, 1997; LeGris et al., 2003; Straub et al., 1997). Some contend that the premise of rational decision-making is flawed, asserting that social dynamics, intuition, and emotions substantially impact technology adoption (Bagozzi, 2007; Chuttur, 2009). The theory's predictive capacity is significantly undermined in complex technological systems when human behaviour is influenced by irrational factors. Notwithstanding these issues, TAT remains a crucial element in contemporary company environments, particularly for leaders and managers seeking to enhance technology utilisation in hybrid workplaces. Leaders may enhance adoption rates and workplace performance by deliberately demonstrating the benefits of technology to employees and organisations (Kim & Chang, 2022).

Methodology

This study adopted survey research design 1,252 junior, middle and senior managers of the selected fast moving consumer goods companies in Lagos State Nigeria. The five FMCG firms selected were Cadbury, Nestlé Nigeria Plc, Unilever Nigeria Plc, Chi, and Dufil Prima. The sample size was determined using Raosoft sample size calculator the Raosoft formula, the estimated sample size was 288 to accommodate cases of non-consent, missing response, drop-out, withdrawal and incompleteness of copies of the questionnaire, the researcher added 30% of the estimated value. In doing this, the study had a total of three hundred and seventy-five (375) as the sample size, and the data were collected using standardized questionnaires. The assessment of internal reliability for the items in the questionnaire was carried out using Cronbach's alpha coefficient. Cronbach coefficient alpha was employed to evaluate the reliability of each individual variable within the questionnaire. To ascertain the reliability of the questionnaire, the independent, dependent, and moderating variables, were subjected to a rigorous reliability test using the SPSS software. The analysis provided valuable insights into the internal consistency and reliability of our questionnaire, helping to ensure the robustness of our research instrument for the study's purposes. The pilot study was considered necessary to determine the willingness of the respondents and to

have a foreknowledge of the reactions of the respondents as well as to ascertain the validity and reliability of the questionnaire when used eventually in the population of the study. For the pilot study, 38 copies of the questionnaire (representing more than 10% of the study sample) were distributed to by the researcher to respondents in an organisation that is not part of the study population as recommended by Ismail et al. (2021). The employees included in the pilot study were junior, middle and senior managers who have hybrid work experience and/or have experience supervising remote employees of GZI industries located in Lagos and Agbara (Ogun State). The research instrument for this study was a structured survey questionnaire adapted by the researcher. The rationale for the use of the questionnaire is because of the high literacy of respondents who are managers in their organisations with experiences of working from home and working in the office. The study used closed-ended questions with the modified six-point Likert type scale. The responses from each item on the questionnaire were answered by rating each question on Very High (VH) = 6, High (H) = 5, Moderately High (MH) = 4, Moderately Low (ML) = 3, Low (L) = 2, and Very Low (VL) = 1. This modified scale is easy to understand and hence helped to increase the reliability of the responses leading to outcomes that are most close to reality from the respondents.

Reliability

Reliability is an internal measure of the instrument's consistency, and it demonstrates its ability to generate comparable and consistent results. A survey instrument with high reliability indicates a high level of consistency. The instrument should be deemed trustworthy when used to measure or gather data, and its outcome should always remain the same once it is achieved. To verify the reliability of the research instrument, the study's reliability was tested using Cronbach's Alpha coefficient and statistical techniques like Cronbach's alpha as well as multiple-item measures. The pre-test results indicated that the scale was deemed reliable (Cronbach's $\alpha > 0.70$) and confirmed the validity of manipulation checks.

Table 1.1: Reliability of Research Instrument

S/N	Variables	Number of Items	Cronbach's alpha	Composite Reliability	Comment
1	Hybrid Work Systems	4	0.852	0.78	Reliable
2	Employee Performance	4	0.798	0.90	Reliable

Source: Researcher's Pilot Study, 2024

Data Analysis and Results

A total number of 375 copies of questionnaire were administered to managers of selected fast moving consumer goods companies in Lagos State Nigeria. A total of two hundred and seventy-seven (277) which represented approximately 73.8% of the total copies of the questionnaire administered were returned and found usable for the analysis. This response rate meets the acceptable threshold where a response rate of 50% is considered adequate, 60% good and 70% is very good (Qalati et al., 2022).

Hypothesis (H₀₁): Hybrid work systems have no significant effect on employee performance.

To test this hypothesis, a multiple regression approach was used. The amalgamated index of hybrid work systems (independent variables) was regressed on the employee performance (dependent variable). The regression outputs were checked to determine if there was a significant change in *R* squared, which could be attributed to the interaction effect of work environment. The results of the analysis are presented in Table 1.2a–c.

Table 1.2a: Model Summary of the Regression Analysis

Model Summary									
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	0.671 ^a	0.450	0.448	5.65621	0.450	225.170	1	275	0.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), Hybrid Work Systems

Source: Researcher's Field Survey, 2024

Table 1.2b: ANOVA of Regression Analysis

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	7203.803	1	7203.803	225.170	0.000 ^b
	Residual	8798.009	275	31.993		
	Total	16001.812	276			
a. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance						

Source: Researcher's Field Survey, 2024

Table 1.2c: Coefficients of the Variables

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
		1	(Constant)	44.908		
	Hybrid Work Systems	0.646	0.043	0.671	15.006	0.000
a. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance						

Source: Researcher's Field Survey, 2024

Interpretation

Table 1.2a presents the results of multiple regression analysis to test how hybrid work systems affect employee performance in selected fast moving consumer goods companies in Lagos State Nigeria. The results for showed R^2 was 0.450 and adjusted R^2 was 0.448. This indicated that hybrid work systems explained 45.0% of the variation in employee performance of selected FMCGs companies in Lagos State, Nigeria. Hence, hybrid work systems and work environment explain 51.3% of the variation in employee performance in FMCGs companies in Lagos State Nigeria.

Tables 1.2b shows an F statistic [$F(1,276)$] of 225.170 with $p < 0.05$ for Model 1. This implies that hybrid work systems have a significant effect on the employee performance of selected FMCGs companies in Lagos State, Nigeria.

Table 1.2c shows the regression coefficient results and revealed that hybrid work systems ($\beta = 0.646$, $t = 15.006$, $p < 0.05$) has a positive and significant effect on employee performance of selected FMCGs companies in Lagos State, Nigeria.

The results suggested that hybrid work systems affect employee performance of selected fast moving consumer goods companies in Lagos State, Nigeria in line with the *apriori* expectation. The regression equation from the analysis is stated as follows:

$$\text{EPE} = 44.908 + 0.646 \text{ HWS} \text{ -----Eqn. 1}$$

Where:

EPE = Employee Performance

HWS = Hybrid Work Systems

The results in Table 1.2a-c and equation 1 indicated that hybrid work systems have a positive effect on employee performance among the selected fast moving consumer goods companies in Lagos State, Nigeria. Based on these findings, null hypothesis one (**H₀₁**), which states that hybrid work systems have no significant effect on employee performance cannot be accepted.

Discussion of Findings

The results of the regression analysis for hypothesis one on the effect of hybrid work systems on employee performance in the fast-moving consumer goods companies in Lagos State, Nigeria, (*Adj. R*² = 0.522; HWS = 1.498, *p* < 0.05) revealed that hybrid work systems are strong predictors of employee performance of the selected fast moving consumer goods companies in Lagos State, Nigeria. These findings provide empirical, theoretical and conceptual implications. The empirical results are consistent with the findings of numerous studies (Atiku et al., 2020; Ekasari et al., 2022; Hackney et al., 2022; Kore et al., 2022; Liu et al., 2021; Moens et al., 2022; Thani et al., 2022; Tunk & Kumar, 2021; Wolor et al., 2021). Kore et al. (2022) discovered that work-from-home policies considerably improve employee performance, particularly when they are accompanied by organisational control and culture. In the same vein, Tunk and Kumar (2021) confirmed that remote work enhances employee performance, while Moens et al. (2022) concluded that it reduces fatigue and increases efficiency. Baakeel (2021) observed that distant work enhances job efficacy and productivity, while Liu et al. (2021) discovered that telework has a positive influence on job performance through job crafting.

Other research indicates that employee performance is influenced by work-from-home arrangements through mediating factors. Choukir et al. (2022) emphasise the mediating functions

of employee attitudes and perceptions in the relationship between job performance and remote employment. Susilo (2020) underscored that the positive effects of work-from-home arrangements on performance are mediated by job satisfaction and motivation. In the same vein, Ishak et al. (2022) discovered that remote workers are more motivated, which in turn improves their job performance. Thani et al. (2022) also observed that the relationship between productivity and remote work is entirely mediated by motivation. Wolor et al. (2021) discovered that work-from-home does not directly impact performance; rather, it enhances work discipline, which in turn improves employee performance. Nevertheless, certain studies suggest that the efficacy of work-from-home is contingent upon a variety of factors. Hackney et al. (2022) noted that the impact is contingent upon the nature of the employment, industry characteristics, and domestic circumstances. The majority of the findings indicate a positive impact, although a few studies report no change or a negative effect. Kitagawa et al. (2021) discovered that remote workers experienced productivity declines as a result of communication difficulties and inadequate home office arrangements. Mukherjee and Narang (2022) identified infrastructural challenges, including electricity disruptions, internet connectivity issues, and work-life balance difficulties, as performance barriers. According to Toscano and Zappala (2020), job satisfaction and productivity are negatively affected by tension and social isolation. In the same vein, Wang et al. (2020) discovered that diminished social support, increased procrastination, and ineffectual communication have a detrimental effect on employee performance in remote work environments.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study examined the effect of hybrid work systems on employee performance in certain fast-moving consumer goods (FMCG) companies in Lagos State, Nigeria. Empirical findings indicated that hybrid work systems have a positive and significant effect on employee performance. The findings indicate that FMCG companies in Lagos State continue to use hybrid work methods that establish clear expectations and provide seamless communication to enhance collaboration. Moreover, businesses that are yet to adopt this strategy have to promote exceptional remote work experiences and invest in remote work facilitators to enhance employee performance. Notwithstanding its contributions, the study has certain limitations that must be considered when evaluating the findings. The research was limited to the FMCG sector in Lagos State, hence restricting the generalisability of the results. Further research should expand the study's scope to

include more industries and geographical regions. The cross-sectional survey research design restricted the capacity to establish causality among hybrid work systems and employee performance. Due to the data being collected at a singular point in time, definitive conclusions on the direction of these associations could not be established. This limitation did not affect the primary objective of the research, which was to examine the impact of hybrid work arrangements on employee performance. Hence, future research may apply a longitudinal methodology to examine how these correlations evolve, providing a deeper understanding of the interplay between Hybrid work and employee performance.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors have disclosed no conflicts of interest.

Author's Affiliation

Egbuta, O. U., Adeoye, S. O. & Elikwu, O. O.

Department of Business Administration and Marketing, School of Management Sciences, Babcock University, Ilishan-Remo, Ogun State, Nigeria

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HOW TO CITE THIS ARTICLE

Magaji, N., Oloidi, S. O., & Soetan, A. T. (2025). Hybrid work systems and employee performance of selected fast moving consumer goods companies in Lagos State, Nigeria. *Seybold Report Journal*, 20(4), 127–146. [DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15236559](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15236559)

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